

DIALLYL DITHIOCARBAMIDOHYDRAZINE—A COLORIMETRIC REAGENT FOR BISMUTH

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The reagent, a colorless and stable compound, gives coloured complexes with Bi, Pd etc. which are extractable with chloroform. The lead, bismuth and cupric complexes have been isolated and analysed, showing the reagent to behave as a dibasic acid. The orange-yellow colour of the bismuth complex in chloroform, obtained by extraction from an aqueous phase at pH 2.4—2.7, is independent of excess of the reagent and proportional to the bismuth content. Bismuth could be estimated colorimetrically in presence of 1000 times its weight of copper in presence of cyanide.

The analytical applications of the compound dithiocarbamidohydrazine, $NH_2CSNH-NHCS-NH_2$, which contains potential mercapto groups coming into operation by enolisation with the neighbouring amino or imino groups, have been the subject of a previous communication (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1949, 8B, 133). The reagent gives a deep yellow colour in a slightly acid solution of bismuth salts which is sufficiently stable for an hour and can be used for the colorimetric estimation of the element. On standing, however, the clear yellow solutions become turbid giving coloured precipitates of indefinite composition. It has been observed that hydrolysis plays an important part in effecting decomposition of the soluble complex.

The present work relates to its diallyl derivative, a colorless and highly stable compound, whose bismuth complex, deep orange in colour, is sparingly soluble in water but extractable with chloroform in which the complex is highly soluble. Removal of the complex from the aqueous phase ensures its greater stability besides offering the obvious advantage of concentrating traces of bismuth present in a large volume of aqueous solution into a small volume of chloroform. Besides, the reagent is recoverable from the chloroform phase by removal of the metal in a strongly acid solution. An analogous reagent is the well known compound, dithizone, which is more sensitive but much less sepecific in action. Besides being difficult to prepare, dithizone is itself coloured and is easily oxidised to a yellow product soluble in chloroform and in carbon tetrachloride. All mono-color methods of colorimetry with dithizone, where excess of the reagent must be removed for its own color, are open to criticism (Sandel, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers, 1944) though good results are obtainable with some metals by working with standards prepared under comparable conditions.

The search for new analytical reagents is primarily justified by the need for more sensitive and/or more selective reactions. The new reagent reported here forms colorless flaky crystals, easily obtained pure by crystallisation from alcohol. It is sparingly soluble in cold water, more so in hot, and easily in alcohol and chloroform. The solubility in chloroform at room temperature (30°) is a little over 2%.

The optimum range of pH in which bismuth is extractable as the orange-yellow complex lies between 2.4 and 2.7 and is independent of the amount of the reagent present in excess. Quantities of bismuth ranging between 0.2 and 1.2 mg. in the form of the complex in 20 c.c. of the chloroform extract, could be easily estimated by visual comparison in the Duboscq colorimeter. The depth of the colour with varying concentration of bismuth follows Beer's law closely.

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Well defined compounds with copper, lead and bismuth have been isolated and their properties studied. The following reactions of the reagent and some allied organic molecules were observed in nearly neutral solutions of cupric and bismuth salts.

TABLE I

Compounds	Reaction with	
	Copper.	Bismuth.
$C_3H_5NH.CS.NHNH.CS.NHC_3H_5$	Black ppt.	Orange-yellow ppt., soluble in chloroform*
$NH_2CSNH.NHCSNH_2$	Black ppt.	Orange colour, not extractable with chloroform
$NH_2CSNHNHCONH_2$	Dark chocolate ppt.	No ppt. or colour
$NH_2CONH.NHCONH_2$	No ppt. or colour	No ppt. or colour

A comparative qualitative study of the above reactions leads to the interesting observation that while only one potential SH group is sufficient to form black cupric derivative, the simultaneous operation of two (SH) groups in 1:6 positions, as in dimercaptodiazole and dithiocarbamidohydrazine, is important in the colour reaction with bismuth. This is an extension of observation made by Dubsy viz., that compounds containing the group (NH.CS.NH) form yellow solutions with bismuth salts, while the grouping (NHCS.NH.CSNH) leads to the formation of red precipitates (Dubsy, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1934, 36, 267).

A procedure for the colorimetry of bismuth with the reagent has been outlined in the present communication. The separation of the element from one thousand times its weight of copper has been effected. The latter is of special interest because minor proportion of bismuth in copper militates against its use for certain purposes.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagent was prepared by the method of Freund and Wischewiansky (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 2878) by refluxing a mixture of allyl mustard oil (40 g.) in alcohol, and hydrazine sulphate (26 g.) mixed with Na_2CO_3 (21 g.). The compound separated as white flakes from the hot filtrate (36 g.), purified by recrystallisation from 90% alcohol, m.p. 177°. [Found (by peroxide fusion) : S, 28.36. Calc. for $C_3H_5NHCSNH.NHCSNHC_3H_5$: S, 27.83 per cent].

It was later found that hydrazine dihydrochloride in place of hydrazine sulphate gave a very pure product though the yield was slightly less.

The reactions of the reagents with some cations in solution were examined. Cu^{++} , Hg^{++} and Co^{++} gave voluminous precipitates in neutral or faintly acid solutions which were quantitative. Bismuth and palladium give orange-coloured, slightly soluble complexes which are extractable in chloroform from slightly acidic solutions. The lead, copper and bismuth complexes were isolated and their compositions established by chemical analysis.

Preparation of Lead Compound.—The lead salt was prepared as a light yellow powder by precipitating from an acetate solution with an acetone solution of the reagent. The precipitate was washed with hot water, rectified spirit and dry acetone, dried in air and finally in a vacuum desiccator. Lead was estimated as sulphate and sulphur by peroxide fusion. [Found : Pb, 47.88 ; S, 14.47. $Pb(C_8H_{12}N_4S_2)$ requires Pb, 47.61 ; S, 14.71 per cent].

Preparation of the Cupric Compound.—The copper compound was prepared by precipitation from a warm 1% solution of copper sulphate acidified with acetic acid with a 2% solution of the reagent in ammonia. The black compound was washed thoroughly with hot water, finally with rectified spirit and dried in a vacuum desiccator. Copper was estimated

iodometrically after decomposition with nitric acid, and sulphur by peroxide fusion. [Found : Cu, 21.70; S, 20.91. $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2)$ requires Cu, 21.81; S, 21.95 per cent].

The black compound is appreciably soluble in organic solvents and is paramagnetic. The gram-molecular susceptibility found with a Guoy magnetic balance is 1.542 Bohr's magneton, without diamagnetic correction for the constituents ($l=9$ cm, $W=0.1936$ g, $\Delta_w=3.8$ mg; $H_{\max}=10.16 \times 10^3$ gauss).

Preparation of the Bismuth Compound.—Pure $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.2 g.) was dissolved in acetone (10 c.c.) containing just sufficient nitric acid to take it into solution. The reagent (1.1 g.) dissolved in acetone (20 c.c.) was now added in the cold with shaking and left overnight in a refrigerator. The solution was then filtered and evaporated in air; the solid redissolved in acetone (40 c.c.) and poured into water (150 c.c.) in a separating funnel, and then extracted with chloroform (30 c.c.). The chloroform extract thus obtained was washed with small amounts of water (10 c.c.) to remove excess acid. Excessive washing causes some of the bismuth compound to go into the aqueous phase.

The orange-red chloroform extract was treated with petroleum ether drop by drop till it was just turbid and then left to evaporate in air. The orange product of the first crystallisation was found to contain some sticky matter. The clear red liquid was decanted from the top and precipitation effected by further addition of petroleum ether. The precipitate formed was filtered at the pump, washed with ether, purified by recrystallisation from chloroform and dried in a vacuum desiccator, yield 2.4 g.

Bismuth was analysed as BiPO_4 and sulphur by peroxide fusion. [Found : Bi, 37.38; S, 17.14. $\text{Bi}_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2)_3$ requires Bi, 37.93; S, 17.42 per cent].

The bright orange-red compound is highly soluble in chloroform. On heating the solid, decomposition starts at 120° and is complete at 210° .

On keeping a water-saturated chloroform solution of the bismuth complex for some hours, an orange-red compound separated slowly. This was isolated, dried in a vacuum desiccator and analysed. [Found : Bi, 45.83; S, 15.12. BiROH (where $\text{R}=\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$) requires Bi, 46.03; S, 14.09 per cent]. It is thus analogous to the methylthiourea compound of bismuth (Varilov, *J. Appl. Chem. U.S.S.R.*, 1938, 11, 363).

Colorimetric Estimation of Bismuth.—A standard solution of bismuth was prepared by dissolving $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck, A.R) in the requisite amount of nitric acid and diluted as required. The bismuth content of the standard solution was determined by estimating bismuth as phosphate.

Colour Comparison at different p_{H} .—In preliminary experiments, a measured quantity of standard Bi-solution was taken in a separating funnel, and dilute HNO_3 of known strength was added in such a way that on making the final volume of 100 c.c. an approximate p_{H} was obtained. Neutral and alkaline solutions were made up in presence of a sufficient quantity of sodium citrate. Then a measured amount of acetone solution of the reagent added and the colour formed was extracted by a measured volume of chloroform. The chloroform extracts were then compared in a Helige colorimeter against a match solution prepared by mixing dilute solutions of potassium dichromate and cobalt nitrate.

TABLE II

Bi taken=1 mg. Reagent taken=10 mg. Total vol. of aq. soln.=100 c.c.
Total vol. of CHCl_3 =10 c.c.

Expt No.	Approx. p_H .	Scale reading for standard match solution.	Scale reading for the extract.
1	1	15	35
2	2	20	28.8
3	3	20	28
4	4	15	22.7
5	5	15	22.5
6	6	15	22.5
7	7	15	26.4
8	9	15	26.1
9	10	15	24.6

The colour formation is maximum around p_H 2. It was observed that a reddish orange bismuth compound separated from the chloroform after 8 to 10 hours. This appears to be the basic bismuth complex formed by hydrolysis from moist chloroform. The colour was, however, stable for one or two days if the chloroform extract was dried with a few pellets of fused CaCl_2 .

Effect of Excess of the Reagent.—The standard bismuth solution (25 c.c. containing 0.001 g. of Bi) was measured into each of four separating funnels, 20 c.c. water and 2 drops of dilute phenolphthalein solution were added to each, and the solutions just neutralised by dilute ammonia followed by drops of dilute nitric acid (1 : 4) to p_H 2 approximately. Different amounts of the reagent dissolved in acetone and greater than the equivalent quantity were now added, the solutions diluted to 100 c.c. and the colours extracted by 10 c.c. of CHCl_3 in each case. The CHCl_3 layers were taken out and the colours compared. It was found that the colour was the same even in presence of over fivefold excess of the reagent.

Optimum p_H range for Maximum Colour.—Keeping the amounts of bismuth and the reagent fixed, different amounts of dilute nitric acid were used, after neutralisation with ammonia. The coloured chloroform extracts were then compared in a colorimeter against a match solution prepared by mixing dilute solutions of potassium dichromate and cobalt nitrate.

The p_H of each aqueous solution after extracting with chloroform was determined by a quinhydrone electrode.

TABLE III

Expt No.	Amount of acid (1.48N).	Amount of Bi=0.001 g. Amount of the reagent=0.004 g.	
		Vol. of aq. soln. before extraction = 100 c.c.	Vol. of CHCl_3 extract = 15 c.c.
		Colorimeter readings with match soln. fixed at 15 of the scale.	p_H .
1	0.5 c.c.	22.4	2.73
2	0.7	22.6	2.56
3	0.9	22.7	2.40
4	1.1	29.6	2.24

Thus a p_H range of 2.4 to 2.7 is suitable for extracting the solution for colorimetric comparison.

Verification of Beer's Law

(a) *By Photo-electric Colorimeter.*—Measured amounts of Bi, taken in separating funnels were diluted to 20 c.c. and neutralised by dilute ammonia, using phenolphthalein as the indi-

cator. The turbidity formed was cleared by adding 1.12 c.c. of normal nitric acid to each, and final volume made up to 100 c.c. A 0.2% solution of the reagent (2 c.c.) in acetone was

FIG. 1.

added to each, and the colour extracted by 10 c.c. of chloroform. The chloroform extracts were collected in dry stoppered flasks and the solutions left in the funnels were washed thrice with 5 c.c. portions of chloroform. The washings were collected with the original extracts which were made up to a final volume of 30 c.c. and dried by adding a few pieces of fused calcium chloride.

The colours were compared in the Lumetron colorimeter (402 EF) using a blue filter (420m μ), taking the percentage transmission of the most dilute solution as the standard. In Fig. 1, optical

densities have been plotted against volumes of bismuth solution (4 mg. Bi/c.c.) taken, showing that Beer's law is followed closely.

TABLE IV

Expt. No.	Amounts of Bi		Ratio A : B	Colorimeter readings		Ratio of colorimeter readings.
	A.	B.		A.	B.	
1	0.2 mg	0.4 mg.	1 : 2	15	7.6	1.97
				20	9.9	2.01
				30	14.9	2.01
2	0.32	0.2	1 : .625	20	32.6	0.613
				30	48.6	0.617
3	0.32	0.4	1 : 1.25	30	24.2	1.24
				40	32.2	1.24
4	0.32	0.6	1 : 1.87	15	7.8	1.91
				30	15.6	1.92
5	0.4	0.8	1 : 2	10	4.8	2.08
				15	7.0	2.02
				20	9.4	2.10
6	0.72	0.6	1 : .833	30	36.3	0.783
				7.5	9.2	0.815
7	0.72	0.8	1 : 1.1	25	24.2	1.03
				30	27	1.1
				20	18.2	1.1
8	0.72	1.0	1 : 1.39	12.5	8.8	1.42
				25	17.9	1.39
				40	27.8	1.44
9	0.72	1.2 mg.	1 : 1.66	30	17.6	1.7
				15	8.9	1.68
				37.5	21.6	1.7
10	0.8	1.0	1 : 1.25	10	7.8	1.28
				20	15.4	1.29
				30	24.2	1.24

(b) *By Duboscq Colorimeter.*—The procedure adopted was the same as that of the previous experiment. The results are shown in Table IV.

Range of Applicability of the Method.—Solutions containing different amounts of bismuth were made up to the same final volume within the same p_n range 2.4—2.7 and extracted with chloroform as described in the preceding experiments. It was found that amounts between 1.2 and 0.2 mg. of bismuth in the solution can be estimated after extraction in 20 c.c. chloroform without difficulty. Beyond these limits the colours are either too deep or too light for visual comparison of colour. The upper limit can, of course, be extended by diluting the chloroform extracts.

Extraction of Bismuth in presence of Copper.—The classical sulphide method for the separation is not satisfactory, specially where the proportion of bismuth is very small. A preliminary concentration by coprecipitation with iron is often necessary.

The present reagent affords a simple and rapid method for estimating 0.1% of bismuth in copper without any preliminary concentration of bismuth. Since by this method bismuth is extracted in a small volume of chloroform the range of applicability can probably be extended by increasing the size of the sample to bring the amount of bismuth within the normal working range of the method.

Measured volumes of standard solutions of copper and bismuth were taken in a separating funnel and made up to 20 c.c. and 0.5 g. of sodium citrate was added and the solution made ammoniacal. The blue solution was then decolorised by adding a concentrated solution of potassium cyanide dropwise, two drops of phenolphthalein were added, and the solution just neutralised by 1.5*N* nitric acid. The final volume was then made up to 100 c.c., 5 c.c. reagent solution in acetone (0.2%) added and the colour formed extracted first by 10 c.c. and later twice with 5 c.c. portions of chloroform. The extracts were made up to 25 c.c. in stoppered measuring cylinders and then dried by a few pieces of fused calcium chloride. A standard was prepared by (a) taking a known amount of bismuth and extracting the colour formed by the reagent with chloroform; (b) mixing a suitable proportion of standard copper sulphate and bismuth nitrate solution and extracting the colour. Both methods were found satisfactory.

TABLE V

Bi taken.	Cu taken.	Bi recovered (mg.).		
0.40 mg.	50.0 mg.	0.3871,	0.3890,	0.3901
0.60	118.8	.5860,	.5883,	.5853
0.60	297.5	.5883,	.6155,	.5940
0.60	500.0	.6060,	.5883,	
0.40	50.0	.3704,	.3606,	
0.60	118.8	.6000,	.5961,	.5971
0.60	500.0	.5883,	.6047,	.5971

Standard burette, pipette, volumetric flasks and one calibrated weight box were used throughout the experiments.